

The observed symptoms did not suggest bacterial or fungal diseases. Instead, observations suggested that biotic agents such as viruses or virus-like organisms may be involved.

In September 1998, symptoms were documented from 11 fields across the outbreak region and 20 samples per field were collected for further testing using different diagnostic techniques. Results showed that only two of the 215 samples gave positive reactions with antisera of rice tungro bacilliform (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical (RTSV) viruses using an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). However, when nucleic acids were extracted from 19 representative plants and amplified by reverse transcriptase polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) using RTSV-specific primers, PCR products were detected. These PCR products even hybridized to a virus-specific probe using a Southern hybridization technique. This confirmed that the collected samples contained nucleic acids of RTSV origin. Since RTBV was not detected by ELISA, Southern hybridization, or electron microscopy, we have no evidence that the collected samples were infected by this second virus. Our results suggest that the outbreak may be due to a virus or virus-like agent related to RTSV alone. Further experiments are needed to confirm these findings.

Vietnam stops registering insecticides for leaffolder control¹

Vo Mai, N.H. Huan, Plant Protection Department, Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam; M.M. Escalada, Visayas State College of Agriculture, Leyte, Philippines; and K.L. Heong, IRRI

Ecological research has shown that because of plant compensation, the highly visible damage caused by rice leaffolders in early crop stages does not result in yield loss. Leaffolder populations are also kept

under natural biological control by a variety of predators. However, farmers in Vietnam often spray insecticides in the early season, believing that without control, leaffolder damage will lead to yield loss. A large proportion of the insecticides used are pesticides known to be highly hazardous to human health (category I under WHO classification). Research has also shown that insecticides applied in the early season tend to disrupt the rice ecosystem, making it more vulnerable to development of secondary pests such as brown planthoppers. Thus, routine sprays are not only uneconomical but also pose health and ecological risks.

In 1992, participatory experiments in the Mekong Delta invited farmers to determine whether chemical control of leaffolders is needed. Hundreds of farmers discovered that yields did not decrease in unsprayed portions of their fields. They therefore changed their perceptions and stopped early-season sprays. To reach millions of farmers, a pilot project was initiated to evaluate the use of communication media to motivate them to participate in this experiment. Using a carefully designed and pretested leaflet, poster, and radio drama, the campaign stimulated a 53% decline in insecticide use, from an average of 3.4 sprays per farmer per season to 1.6. Most farmers stopped sprays in the tillering and booting stages. Other provinces in the Mekong Delta adopted the approach and, in 1997, the campaign reached 92% of the 2.5 million farmers, reducing insecticide sprays to an average of 1.

These research results helped to convince the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development to stop registering insecticides for leaffolder control. In a letter, the Director General of the Plant Protection Department advised pesticide companies that the Department no longer considers leaffolder control as a justification for registering insecticides. This policy is expected to contribute toward a further reduction in unnecessary insecticide use.

Short- to medium-duration rice in rotation with chickpea in Bangladesh

M.A. Mazid and I.U. Mollah, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Rajshahi; E. Haque, Directorate of Agricultural Extension, Tanore, Bangladesh; and L.J. Wade, IRRI

We experimented with growing medium-duration BRRI Dhan 32 (BR32) (125-130 d) rice followed by short-duration Barichola 2 chickpea (115-120 d) as an alternative to the traditional, long-duration, transplanted-aman rice (145-150 d) main crop in rainfed lowlands of northwest Bangladesh. The conditions were quite favorable in 1998, with BR32 yielding about 4.5 t ha⁻¹, Swarna (a long-duration modern variety) about 5.0 t ha⁻¹, and the traditional long-duration varieties about 3.0-3.5 t ha⁻¹. Heavy rains of up to 140 mm just after harvest of BR32 delayed establishment of Barichola 2 chickpea in some areas, negating to some extent the advantage of an earlier BR32 harvest. Under these conditions, however, farmers who recognized the need to establish chickpea quickly should still have a satisfactory chickpea harvest.

Innovative farmers, such as Mr. M.D. Alauddin of Telopara, Tanore, broadcast the chickpea into the rice stubble and then crossplowed. Despite the rough seedbed, the large-seeded chickpea established well, showing good growth and good seed set. We observed that any delay in chickpea establishment severely affected chickpea growth. Crop stand was good when land was prepared before sowing, but crop growth was less.

At sites where planting was delayed (e.g., where flooding interfered with sowing), chickpea had poor crop stand and poor growth, but linseed performed better. Some farmers tried lentil, but it could not cope with no rain at all. Using a shorter duration rice variety, followed by a shorter duration chickpea variety, is one cropping practice that may prove advantageous to farmers in rainfed areas of Bangladesh.

¹ Editor's note: Dr. Vo Mai was awarded the Distinguished Service medal for her contributions to Vietnam agriculture, which included her role in this project, and Dr. K.L. Heong was awarded the Medal for Agricultural Development in Vietnam by the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, for his contributions to the project and Vietnam agriculture.